

THE IMPACT OF SATELLITE TELEVISION PROGRAMS ON THE ACQUISITION AND LEARNING OF ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

It is a consensus among linguists that language acquisition occurs in the context of societal interaction. Hence, a child's cognitive development will largely be influenced by the adults through whom he acquires language and gets acculturated. This tends to limit the sources of acquisition to the immediate environment of the child. However, today's global world creates a different situation, especially in many Nigerian homes. The proliferation of Satellite television, almost limitless possibilities in the film industry, and majorly in animations has created a global society within the homes of most elite families. Children's cartoons have become so realistic and interactional, and children's exposure to television has become so regular and significant that their language acquisition/language learning is impacted by it. Employing the perspectives of Vygotsky's Interactionist Theory of language learning, this paper explores the impact of the virtual global world to which children are exposed through satellite television children programs. The paper adopted the descriptive survey research design. The study sample comprises twenty children consisting of 2 children from each of the selected 10 families. A simple random sampling technique was used in selecting the 20 children. It is found that children exposed to regular viewing of children's cartoons acquire a cognitive ability that surpasses the physical exposure to adult language use in their immediate society. Recommendations are thereby proffered.

Keywords: Satellite-Television, Language Acquisition, Language Learning, Cartoons

Introduction

Like any other natural language, the English language is a social phenomenon that has relevance only in social settings. It is either acquired in society as a first language or learnt as a second or foreign language. Scholars have established that “It is impossible to imagine the development of society without language and the development of language without society” (Mamadaliyeva, 2021). Hence, Vygotsky (1978) posits that language can only be acquired through interaction in a society. Thus, language acquisition occurs in a package that includes the culture and collective knowledge of society. In other words, society and language are mutually indispensable. Language is thus a very complex human phenomenon which has proved challenging to define, as several definitions have been found inadequate. Crystal (2010) defines language as a system of conventional, spoken or written symbols by which human beings communicate as members of a social group and participants in its culture. Hence, the definition submits that language occurs in a society. Therefore, children acquire the language of the society along with all the features of pronunciation, grammar, lexical items and cultural perspectives of the society. Simply put, they speak like they are spoken to.

The Nigerian child will thus speak like a Nigerian. When the Nigerian child begins to switch between speaking like a Nigerian child and speaking like an American, for example, there is a need to question the theories of language acquisition and learning and their postulations. For instance, David requested a biscuit, and his mother refused to give him one. He responded by saying, “Aw awww! He turned away, drooping his shoulders with arms dangling and back slouched in a typical cartoon pose of dejection. Her mother did not understand the pose and fiercely instructed David to “stop walking like that and walk normally”. David has acquired some socio-linguistic characteristics that her mother was not aware of. Such is the situation in many families where Satellite television has created an extended society for the Nigerian child who is exposed to a tangible amount of television viewing. In other words, like many Nigerian children from elite homes, David has acquired linguistic and cultural characteristics outside the linguistic characteristics of the society in which he has acquired language.

Review of Literature

The use of English in the world and, by implication, in Nigeria has a significant bearing on our learners as world citizens. The English language, though a mother tongue to native speakers, is a second and foreign language to many people in the world, of which Nigeria is inclusive (UBE, 2010). As a result of the numerous functions the language performs in Nigeria, it has continued to grow steadily on a daily basis. For instance, English is used in education, not just as a teaching subject but also as the language of instruction in Nigerian schools from upper primary to tertiary institutions (NPE, 2004). It is a compulsory subject required to study any course in any

institution of learning in Nigeria. It is used in the media, Nigerian politics, commerce and international frontiers.

For learners of the English Language as a second or foreign language, access to the use of the language in society is rare. This is, however, changing with Nigerian children as they are exposed to the language in use via satellite television. Poštič (2015) observes that increasing numbers of Bangladeshi students spoke English with an almost pure American accent, including intonation. They found that this resulted from their viewing of American programs on television. The channels available on TV have been multiplied greatly by the introduction of cable and satellite television, which allows a variety of TV programs to be viewed round the clock, day and night. For the children, cartoon network is an irresistible choice (Tamba, 2022)

Children in the ages range between zero and ten years are typically drawn to cartoons on TV. According to Singleton (1989), this is the period when a child has the chance to reach a near-native competence in the pronunciation of English. Clark (2000), in a study on the pedagogical value of cartoons, found that cartoons engage learners' attention, create a conducive atmosphere for learning, and thus improve their ability to think and discuss. Doring (2002) explains that language learners exposed to cartoons can produce very productive and interesting oral answers. Scheffler and Baranowska (2023) also found in their study that watching videos significantly improved the recognition of how words are pronounced. The value of cartoons in teaching is further underscored by Bahrani and Sim (2012), who posit that children with a low ability to learn language can be significantly improved through exposure to cartoons. Thus, through satellite television, especially cartoons (which are children's favourite choices), English learners are attracted to the speakers' language and are also stimulated to speak the language. (Haque 2013).

Theoretical Framework

Perspectives of Vygotsky's interactionist theory of language learning are employed in this study. Lev Vygotsky was a Russian psychologist best known for his sociocultural theory who believed that social interaction plays a critical role in children's learning. Through such social interactions, children go through a continuous process of learning. Vygotsky sociocultural theory of human learning describes learning as a social process and the origination of human intelligence in society or culture (1978). The central theme of Vygotsky's theoretical framework is that social interaction plays a fundamental role in the development of cognition. Vygotsky believed that children acquire language as a result of engaging in social experiences. The interactionist approach (sociocultural theory) combines ideas from sociology and biology to explain how language is developed. According to this theory, children learn language out of a desire to communicate with the world around them and language emerges from and is dependent upon social interaction. Vygotsky was of the view that learning has its basis in interacting with other people.

The apparent social interaction a typical Nigerian child from an elite home is expected to be involved in includes his immediate family and peers at home and in school. In a typical setting, all of these speak the Nigerian variety of English. This paper observed, however, that the social

interaction that such a child is involved in includes an extension into the social environment created on television cartoons and other children's programs on cable television and according to the interactionist theory of language acquisition, children who are exposed to this extended social interaction on cable television, should acquire language from it.

Statement of the Problem

Satellite or cable television has become very common in Nigeria with the introduction of cheaper decoders and cheaper viewing packages. Most elite homes thus have at least one of such decoders, and many homes have one dedicated to the viewing pleasure of the children who are drawn naturally to the cartoon networks. Coupled with the fact that most elite homes feature busy parents, children are often kept engaged in front of the television, which they often view for hours on end. One of the results of this is that Nigerian children from elite homes develop in a community which is extended into the virtual society on television. Since language is acquired in society, one must ask: for a child like David, who lives with his parents and attends a local daycare, where did the exclamatory expression "Aw awww!" and the drooping pose come from? In view of this, this paper interrogates the extended society on satellite televisions as a source for the acquisition of British and/or American English among Nigerian children.

Significance of the Study

Findings from this study are significant for developing methods of improving English language skills in Nigerian children, especially in achieving mutual intelligibility among British, American and Nigerian English speakers. It could also be effectively employed in incorporating cartoons into the teaching and learning of the English Language among Nigerian children.

Research Questions

The study was designed to proffer answers to the following research questions (henceforth "RQ").

RQ1: Do children spend enough time before the television to acquire a language or its features?

RQ2: Are lexical features of British and/or American English noticeable in the use of language by the children studied?

RQ3: Are phonological features of British and/or American English evident in the use of language by the children studied?

RQ4: Are grammatical features of British and/or American English noticeable in the use of language by the children studied?

RQ5: Do the children code switch between the British /American and the Nigerian varieties of English?

Research Methodology

A descriptive survey design was adopted for this study. The instrument used for this study was a self-designed questionnaire tagged “Impact of Satellite Television Programs on Acquisition and Learning of English as a Second Language in Nigeria”. The instrument was validated by research experts whose corrections were strictly adhered to. The questionnaire was in two parts- part A required the respondents to supply their bio-data, while part B comprised open and closed-ended items. The researchers personally administered the questionnaire to enhance good responses from the respondents. The analysis was done using both descriptive and inferential statistics.

Data Analysis

RQ 1: Do children spend enough time before the television to acquire a language or its features?

Question 1. Do your children watch programs on cable television?

Figure 1. Children watch Satellite television.

Figure 1 shows that 100% of the respondents' children are exposed to satellite television, affirming that most children from elite homes have their social environment extended into the environments created on TV programs.

Question 2. From what age have they been watching cable TV?

Figure 2. Age of children on the first day behind the screen

Figure 2 shows that 80% of the respondents have allowed their children to watch television by age 1. 15% claimed that their children started between 2 and 3 years, 5% claimed they started

between 4 and 5 years, and none started as late as 6 years. This indicates that children get exposed to television at the same time considered most crucial to language acquisition.

Question 3. How many days of the week do they watch television?

Figure 3. Number of Days of TV Viewing

Figure 3. shows that 35% of the respondents place the average number of days their children watch TV in a week at less than three days, while 45% of them posit that their children watch TV more than 3 days in a week, and 20% reveal that their children watch TV every day. This shows that children watch television for a significant number of days in the week, indicating that the TV could have an impact on their developmental processes.

Question 4. What is the average number of hours they spend watching TV per day?

Figure 4. Daily Exposure to the TV

Table 4 shows that 45% of the respondents stated an average viewing time of 1 hour for their children, 35% opted for 2 to three hours, 25% picked 4 to 5 hours, and five percent picked over five hours. Since children of 80% of respondents spend 2 to five hours per day watching TV, the time spent watching in front of the screen and the virtual society it creates is significant enough for them to acquire language features from this source.

Question 2. Does the average time spent watching TV increase during the holidays?

Figure 2. More Television on Holidays

95% of respondents agree that children do more of television viewing during their holidays, while only five percent of them disagree. The implication of this is that even more exposure to television viewing occurs during school holidays.

The preceding shows the extent to which children are exposed to television, especially cartoons, which take up more of the time they spend viewing TV. This provided an affirmative response to research question 1. Thus, children spend enough time watching satellite television to be able to acquire a language or features of a language.

RQ 3: Are lexical features of British and/or American English noticeable in the use of language by the children studied?

Question 2.1. Do your children use English words you are not familiar with?

Figure 6: Lexical Evidence of Acquisition

Figure 6 shows that 90% of the respondents have observed lexical items in their children's diction that were novel to them as parents and which they have traced to some of the cartoons they watched on TV. 45% of them agreed with an emphatic yes, while another 45% stated that they sometimes observe such novel lexical items. 10% of them did not observe such new words in the diction of their children. This shows that the extended societies of the children made them acquire new words in the English Language.

Question 2.2.: Do they know the names of animals/plants that you do not?

Figure 7: foreign Nature Awareness

Figure 7 shows that 5% of the respondents are sure that their children knew such names of Animals and plants. 40% said they did sometimes, and another 35% affirmed that they did. However, 20% of the Parents posit that their children did not know the names of animals they were unaware of. Since many cartoon programs children watch have animal characters, many of

which are geared towards creating awareness of nature and its preservation, children are exposed to names and characteristics of animals and plants. Since this data shows evidence of awareness of animals and plants beyond the experience available in the immediate environment of respondents' children, it shows that acquisition and learning are taking place through their television viewing.

Question 2.3.: Do they talk about things you are not familiar with?

Figure 8: Novel Experiences

Figure 8 shows that 65% of respondents have observed that their children discussed ideas and things that they, as parents, were not familiar with. An additional 25% of respondents agree that their children sometimes do the same. 10%, however, did not know of their children discussing such novel experiences. Since language is also a tool of acculturation, this shows that the children had experiences outside their immediate social experience.

The foregoing shows that children have acquired words and expressions that their parents are unfamiliar with. This implies that they have experiences beyond that which their parents have exposed them to in their homes. This indicates that their social experiences and, consequently, their acquisition of language are not limited to their immediate home environment.

RQ 4: Are phonological features of British and/or American English evident in the use of language by the children studied?

Question 3.1. Have you heard them speak in an American or British accent?

Figure 9: British/American Accent?

Figure 9 shows that 30% of the respondents believe their children use either the British or American accent in their speech, 55% believe their children do so sometimes, and 5% were unsure. However, 10% of the respondents believe their children did not speak with American or

British accents. Accent is one of the most evident traces of a different variety of a language. The percentage of parents found to have noticed that their children could speak with some accent here indicates that Nigerian children under this study might be capable of speaking the English Language with an accent that they acquired outside their homes and immediate society.

Question 3.2.: Do they speak like the cartoon characters they watch on TV?

Figure 10: Cartoon Characters as Models

According to Table 10, 65% of the respondents agree that their children sometimes speak like their favourite cartoon characters, and another 25% agree that their children mimic the characters. Only 10% of the respondents feel that their children did not mimic their cartoon characters. This trend shows that the children, in acting their favourite characters in plays, practice speaking like them, thus building their skills in English speech with the accent of the characters.

Since children mimic and use the British or American speech mannerisms of their cartoon characters when they play. The children thus have acquired phonological features of these varieties of English since the cartoon networks use these varieties of the English Language.

RQ 5: Do the children code switch between the British /American and the Nigerian variety of English?

Question 4.1: Do they change the tone of their English speech at different times?

Figure: 11: Code Switching

Figure 11 shows that 85% of respondents agreed that their children switch between their everyday speech and British/ American accents, and another 5% say their children did so sometimes. 10% did not agree that their children sometimes switch their accents.

This also indicates an acquisition that could be traced to television viewing. More importantly, it shows that they can be kept apart and children can switch between them like different languages.

Discussion and Recommendation

Findings from this study show that children spend much time watching cable television. Such viewing extends their experiences beyond their immediate environments into those created on television. They thus acquire English language features, such as American accents, which are foreign to their homes but used frequently on their favourite programs on cable TV. The study also shows that these children had started watching TV from their formative ages, during which their language acquisition device was still active. This points to the possibility of acquiring the language(s) or varieties of language(s) they are exposed to on TV. Acquiring language, however, requires substantial exposure to the language. The study finds that most children watch TV more than three days a week. This is a significant exposure to the language of their TV program if the number of hours spent watching TV is substantial for each day. Findings of the study show that most of the children spend a significant length of time watching TV each day. The fact that the time spent watching TV increases for almost all children during holidays underscores the adequacy of the length of time. Thus, It is not surprising that the parents' responses show evidence of such language acquisition.

It must be noted that the use of language cannot be separated from culture. It is thus recommended that because the children could acquire foreign cultures along with the language, parents must ensure adequate and consistent parental guidance for their children even when they watch programs rated for general view. Since language acquisition is found to be possible through exposure to television programs, it is recommended that the types of TV programs that interest children should be explored in the teaching and learning process, especially in teaching a second or foreign language.

Conclusion

Satellite television is an extension of the social realities of Nigerian children, especially those from elite homes. Since language is acquired or learnt in society, the several hours of viewing programs on television provide a platform for the acquisition of the English language. Children spend enough time watching television several days of a week. Many would spend even more time in front of the television if allowed. This is usually because of their interest in cartoons and other television shows they find very irresistible. While attention has not been paid to specific satellite television programs in this study, findings have shown that generally, children get so involved in the settings, actions and lines spoken in the shows that they become, for them, an extended reality with which they interact and acquire the English language.

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